

Health Sector Corruption and Access to Healthcare in Africa*

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Abstract

Using Afrobarometer data, we show that respondents living in sub-national regions in which corruption in the health sector is more common are more likely to report that they have had to go without medical care for themselves or their family regularly or lack access entirely. We also show that corruption in other aspects of the public administration is not significantly associated with access to health care, suggesting that when it comes to improving access to healthcare, fighting medical corruption is of primary importance. For those who have accessed medical care, the regional incidence of medical corruption predicts more difficulty in terms of obtaining the care that they needed. We conclude that medical corruption not only restricts access to medical care, but also degrades the quality of the service for those able to access the system.

Keywords: Africa, bribery, corruption, health, healthcare

JEL Classification: D73, I10, K4, O10, O55

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Introduction

Expanding access to healthcare is a key objective of national governments around the world, and of international agencies and non-governmental organisations. The availability of healthcare is among the important influences of life and death (Sen, 1998). While progress has been made in many countries, life expectancy remains low by international standards and maternal and infant mortality remains high (World Bank, 2022). For example, in 2020, while life expectancy at birth is estimated to be 72.26 years on average worldwide, in Africa it is estimated to be only 60.85 years (World Bank, 2022). Similarly, infant mortality per 1000 live births in Africa, estimated at 51.1, is higher than the world average of 28.9. The same is true for under-five mortality per 1000 live births: 75.1 in Africa compared to a world average of 38.7. Universal health coverage (UHC) is a key target of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3 and the African Union's Agenda 2063. However, World Health Organisation (WHO) data shows that in many countries, coverage remains low (WHO, 2023). The 2019 regional average of the WHO's UHC Service Coverage Index is 79 in Europe but only 46 in Africa.

While healthcare outcomes are a function of many economic, social, and political factors, there is reason to believe that corruption, the abuse of public power for private gain (Klitgaard, 1988; Klitgaard et al., 2000), plays an important role in determining access to healthcare. Figure 1 shows that countries with poor control of corruption (as measured by the World Bank's Control of Corruption metric) tend to have low UHC Service Coverage.

Corruption can take different forms in the health system, the most direct and immediate of which is bribery. Hunt (2007) finds that people who have been victims of misfortune are more likely to be the targets of bribes. In the context of healthcare, patients, or their families, who are in urgent need of medical care make for easy targets for corrupt healthcare workers and administrators. Corrupt health officials and health workers may seek bribes in exchange for access to healthcare or to speed up the provision of a particular service. Corruption also affects decision making at a very fundamental level within the medical system. Rönnerstrand and Lapuente (2017), using Eurobarometer data, find that, there is a strong positive association between corruption and antibiotics use. Corrupt health officials and health workers may also steal or misuse equipment and embezzle from health budgets and patient funds (Vian and Crable, 2017). Healthcare corruption can also take the form of administrative corruption, bribery in medical service delivery, embezzlement of

medicine and medical devices, improper marketing relations, insurance fraud, procurement corruption, and state capture (Vian and Crable, 2017).

Figure 1. Control of corruption and UHC service coverage in Africa

Corruption also affects the composition of public expenditures (Croix and Delavallade, 2007; Delavallade, 2006; Mauro, 1998) which in turn can adversely affect health sectors through reduced funding allocation (Azfar and Gurgur, 2008; Gupta et al., 2001; Vian and Crable, 2017). In all these ways, corruption can plausibly lead to diminished healthcare capacity and block access for those who need it.

The literature also supports the conclusion that corruption has detrimental effects on health outcomes. Corruption affects the quality of health services, increases costs and reduces the volume of health care, thereby limiting access to health care for patients, especially the poorest (Azfar and Gurgur, 2008; Gupta et al., 2001; Vian and Crable, 2017). For example, informal payments by patients contribute to higher costs of care. In doing so, less affluent citizens may not obtain basic health services because of their inability to pay, thereby exacerbating health inequalities. Li et al. (2017) find that corruption significantly increases mortality rates and reduces life expectancy and immunization rates. Investigating the relationship between corruption and infant mortality in Turkey, Dincer and Teoman (2019) find that increases in corruption track with increases in infant mortality in the long-run. This echoes the finding of Ortega et al. (2013) that corruption undermines the growth of the health component of the Human Development Index.

However, no studies to our knowledge, have investigated and quantified the effects of medical corruption on access to medical care in Africa. The work which is closest to our own is Hsiao et al. (2019) who find, using Afrobarometer data, that those who have paid bribes in the health sector are more likely to report difficulty in obtaining medical care. However, they do not examine the link between health sector corruption at a more aggregate level and individual access to medicine and medical treatment.

We contribute to this literature by looking at the effects of corruption on healthcare access rather than on specific health outcomes. The Afrobarometer surveys allow us to do this as they ask respondents about their access to medical care. These large-scale representative surveys also allow us to look specifically at corruption in healthcare as opposed to generalised measures of corruption perceptions or counts of corruption convictions for crimes committed in any sector of society. They also allow us to create regional indicators of the incidence of bribery in healthcare and ask if the level of medical corruption, over and above one's own experience of paying a bribe, is important in terms of access to healthcare. In other words, our interest is in the question of whether a corrupt healthcare system has consequences for the population's ability to access care, and whether they themselves can or will pay bribes to access care.

We find that respondents who live in regions with a greater incidence of medical corruption are less likely to report that they have access to medical care. We further show that the local incidence of other types of bribery does not predict access. We find little evidence of different effects for women and men. Finally, we find that for those who do access healthcare, corruption is associated with the view that it was difficult to obtain the care that they needed. Taken together, our results are consistent with corruption reducing access to and undermining the quality of the care that those who can get into the system received.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. In the next section, we explore further the established relationships between corruption and health expenditures and outcomes. We then present our methods and data before presenting our findings. We conclude with a discussion of the implications and limitations of our work and some suggestions for future research.

Corruption and Health Care

It has long been argued that corruption affects the composition of public expenditure (Croix and Delavallade, 2007; Delavallade, 2006; Mauro, 1998). According to Liang and Mirelman (2014) the most corrupt countries allocate fewer public resources to the health

sector, which provides less rent-seeking opportunities for officials and the government than other components of public expenditure (physical capital, housing, etc.). This implies that controlling corruption facilitates the allocation of public expenditure to the health sector (Liang and Mirelman, 2014).

The level of corruption also affects the choice of governments on how to spend resources allocated to the health sector. Vian (2008a, 2000b) reports that in a corrupt environment, authorities are more likely to prioritize the construction of hospitals and the purchase of expensive, high-tech equipment because of the rents associated with these types of investments that are subject to lucrative contracts. This choice is made at the expense of primary health care programmes such as immunization and family planning.

In many cases, bribery negatively correlates with people's access to healthcare (Belli et al., 2004; Falkingham, 2004; Liaropoulos et al., 2008). For example, Hunt (2010) shows that in Uganda bribery is associated with worse health care for the briber, thus undermining the goal of increased access to health care. In the health sector, corruption could reduce access to quality medical care by inflating the cost of health projects, draining resources, and delaying upgrading and essential repair work of health infrastructure and equipment.

Corruption can discourage the use of public health facilities, impose restrictions on the consumption of health services, reduce immunization rates and delay the vaccination of newborns. It reduces citizens' satisfaction with health services, erodes trust in the public component of the health system and increases waiting times in health centres (Azfar and Gurgur, 2008; Habibov, 2016; Radin, 2013; Nair et al., 2017). The low quality of public health services resulting from poor governance leads some users to turn to private health services. This disinterest reduces their willingness to pay for public health services, encourages tax evasion behaviour, and limits the government's ability to provide quality services over time (Gupta et al., 2001). When people's trust in the health system is undermined, this can lead to underutilization of health services or increase the likelihood that they will not seek care or complete their medical treatment. It may also lead them to resort to other types of treatment and self-medication which may be harmful to their health (Hsiao et al., 2019).

Inadequate supervision by regulatory bodies, laxity, and insufficient controls due to corruption can lead to absenteeism of health workers in public facilities (Friedman, 2018; Lewis and Pettersson, 2009; Vian and Crable, 2017). In the case of absenteeism, health workers are paid but do not show up for work. This is another form of corruption that affects staffing in the public health service. Public health staff prefer to spend more time on private

sector activities at the expense of the public hospital. This slows down the normal functioning of health services and creates a congestion effect (Houensou and Saliga, 2019).

Corruption can result in the use of public facilities for private purposes, and the practice of medical professions by unqualified and under-qualified personnel. It can also lead to the marketing of fake or poor-quality medicines on the market and a shortage of medicines available in public facilities, due to theft and diversion to private pharmacies, all of which are detrimental to health. Vian and Crable (2017) report that 4% of deaths of children in 40 African countries are related to the use of poor-quality medicines for the treatment of malaria. The use of poor quality or fake medicines can contribute to the development of treatment-resistant organisms and increase the risk of spreading communicable diseases.

The relationship between patients and health professionals presents a risk of corruption due to information asymmetry and demand for health services that is largely inelastic (Vian, 2008a, 2008b). The prevalence of information asymmetry problems in the health sector can create abuses in the sector (Holmberg and Rothstein, 2010). Indeed, different actors may take advantage of their privileged position for personal gain, including the government regulator¹, the payer (social security, private or public health insurance), the provider (public or private), suppliers of drugs and equipment, and patients (Savedoff and Hussmann, 2006). For example, the discretionary power of health professionals to decide which medicines and in what quantities are needed can increase these risks of abuse (Vian, 2008b). Physicians may become psychologically and financially dependent on pharmaceutical companies because of the donations they receive from them. They may return the favour by prescribing drugs produced by these pharmaceutical companies (Light et al., 2013; Sah and Fugh-Berman, 2013). Such mechanisms could explain the relationship between corruption and unhealthy antibiotic abuse. For example, patients may request or be asked to undergo inappropriate medical treatment in exchange for a bribe (Di Tella and Savedoff, 2001). The health sector is particularly vulnerable to corruption in the drug sector. As a result, countries are regularly subject to significant trafficking in pharmaceuticals. The fact that information is highly asymmetric between consumers and producers means that the patient cannot check the quality of medicines in advance and must rely on information provided either by the medicine producer or by health service providers.

¹ This can be thought of as state capture in that policies and laws that are supposed to benefit the public interest have instead been influenced or 'captured', often through bribes, by private interests. Regulators captured by the healthcare industry they regulate lose their objectivity and become less able to monitor and sanction corruption. This affects the level playing field and creates systemic inequalities.

Although in many cases corruption is negatively correlated with people's health outcomes (Belli et al., 2004; Falkingham, 2004; Liaropoulos et al., 2008), it has also been argued that corruption can “grease the wheels” of an economy by allowing people to bypass costly and inefficient regulation and red tape (Huntington, 1968; Leff, 1964; Leys, 1965; Lui, 1985). Some argue that corruption has positive aspects, at least for the bribers, such as the creation of a better and continuous relationship between health personnel and patients (Vian et al., 2012). This means that theoretically, bribes can have either positive or negative effects on the supply side. Prendergast (1999) highlights that following the principal-agent theory, financial rewards can incentivize workers to work harder and smarter. However, according to Holmstrom and Milgrom (1991) financial incentives can motivate workers to focus on quantity more than quality when tasks are complex because quantity is easier to measure. Thus incentives, such as corruption or other “rewards” can undermine the quality of work. Access to medical care might be intentionally reduced by health service providers to induce more payments.

Data and Methodology

Corruption can occur in many different sectors and is often categorized as grand or petty. We have learned a great deal from composite indicators such as Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), World Bank's Control of Corruption. However, such metrics cannot distinguish between different types of corruption or point to where it occurs. They are also based on perceptions of corruption which can differ from reality (Mackey et al., 2018; Razafindrakoto and Roubaud, 2010; Rose-Ackerman and Palifka, 2016; Seligson, 2006). Country level measures of corruption perceptions are well known for being prone to measurement errors. For example, Svensson (2003), Reinikka and Svensson (2006), Treisman (2007), and Fan et al. (2009) have highlighted the issue with perception biases in standards corruption measures whereby corruption is inferred from a hypothesised consequence of corruption – such as a low-quality health system. Corruption perception metrics have also been criticised for being slow to keep up with new developments (Kenny, 2009; Knack, 2007). Survey data on people's experiences, however, allow us to capture corruption in different aspects of daily life and examine the consequences (Reinikka and Svensson, 2006).

The Afrobarometer is a series of representative household surveys of socio-economic conditions and political attitudes that are carried out in African countries. The data are collected from face-to-face surveys with respondents randomly chosen to ensure a nationally

representative sample. The response rate to the survey averages more than 75%. We employ the eighth round of the Afrobarometer, which was conducted in 34 African countries² from 2019 to 2022.³ The seventh round introduced important methodological improvements, namely computer-assisted data collection. Demarest (2017) notes that “Switching to Computer Assisted Personal Interviewing (CAPI) can reduce mistakes during the interview (and data input) process but can also allow for the systematic collection of data on interview duration and speed per question, the tracking of interviewer walk patterns via GPS coordinates, as well as the time between interviews. Logan et al. (2020) also identify CAPI as an important element in collecting high quality data. CAPI helps to ensure that random walk rules are followed, helping to avoid “biases in the pools of respondents recruited by interviewers” (Demarest, 2017). We therefore focus our analysis on the most recent data collected under the reformed methodology - the eighth round - and show that our main findings are robust to using the previous round. The surveys enable us to test the impact of medical corruption on access to health care because they contain a range of questions on basic human needs and experiences, including access to medical care, and experiences of corruption in several contexts.

To measure household access to medical care, we utilize responses to the following survey question: “Over the past year, how often, if ever, have you or anyone in your family: Gone without medical care?”. The possible answers are “never”, “just once or twice”, “several times”, “many times”, and “always.” On average 44.46% of respondents have gone several times, many times or always without medical care in Africa. In Guinea, Senegal, Angola, Sudan, Zimbabwe, and Côte d'Ivoire the situation is even worst: more than 54.17% of respondents have gone several times, many times or always without medical care.

To measure corruption in the health sector, we use questions that ask the respondents if they pay bribes for treatment at public clinics or hospitals: “How often, if ever, did you have to pay a bribe, give a gift, or do a favour for a health worker or clinic or hospital staff in order to get the medical care you needed?”⁴ Respondents can answer “Never”, “once or twice”, “a few times”, and “often”. We create a dummy variable from this information, which

²The list of countries in the sample: Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Malawi, Mali, Mauritius, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe.

³ The data and full methodology can be obtained from <https://www.afrobarometer.org>

⁴ This definition is larger than that provided by Lewis (2007) as informal payments in the form of cash or in-kind transfers to health service providers tend to be significant as at least official payment.

takes a value of one if the respondents say that they have at least paid a bribe once and zero if they never did so.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for the full sample

Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD	Min	Max.	Description
Access to medical care	47,909	1.335	1.311	0	4	“Over the past year, how often, if ever, have you or anyone in your family gone without medical care?” The possible answers are 0=Never, 1=Just once or twice, 2=Several times, 3=Many times, 4=Always.
Medical bribery experience	48,029	0.114	0.317	0	1	Dummy variable, equals 1 if the respondent has any medical bribery experience
Regional incidence of medical corruption	48,084	0.114	0.101	0	0.65	Average of medical bribe for all those in the same region as the respondent.
Health infrastructure	47,660	0.606	0.488	0	1	Are the following facilities present in the primary sampling unit/enumeration area, or within easy walking distance: Health clinic? Equals 1 if there a health clinic and 0 if not.
Education	47,909	2.212	1.204	1	5	“What is your highest level of education?”. It takes the value of 1 if respondents have “Less than full primary» education level, 2 if “Primary or Some Secondary”, if 3 “Secondary», 4 “Post-Secondary Qualification or Some University”, 5 if they have “University Complete and Postgraduate”
Poverty	47,844	0.158	0.365	0	1	Over the past year, how often, if ever, have you or anyone in your family: Gone without a cash income? Dummy variable, equals 1 if they have gone without cash and zero otherwise .
Urban area	48,084	0.453	0.498	0	1	Equals 1 if the primary sampling unit is urban and zero otherwise
Female	48,084	0.500	0.500	0	1	Equals 1 if the respondent is female.
Age	48,072	37.068	14.794	18	120	“How old are you?”. It measures the age of the respondent.

We estimate ordered probit models in which the dependent variable captures access to medical care. Employing ordered probit models allows us to use all the available information in the question on access to medicine and medical treatment. We report the marginal effects to facilitate the interpretation of the results. In line with previous studies on health access or outcomes, we control for a range of important factors. We consider sociodemographic and economic variables including age, gender, urban status, education, and poverty. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of each of the variables used in this article and provides a description of how the variables are coded.

Table 1 shows that 11 % of people in our sample have had some experience of bribery in the health sector. 45.3 % of people in our sample live in urban areas. 50% of respondents are female, with very small variations across the countries. The average age of people in our sample is 37.1 years. Approximately 60.60% of respondents lived in an area where the enumerator noted a health clinic within easy walking distance.

To estimate the relationship between medical corruption and access to medical care, we estimate ordered probit models of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Pr(\text{medical}_{ij} = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4) & \\
 &= \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{medbribe}_i + \beta_2 \text{regmedbribe}_j + \beta_3 \text{healthinfrast}_i \\
 &+ \beta_4 \text{female}_i + \beta_5 \text{age}_i + \beta_6 \text{poverty}_i + \beta_7 \text{urban}_i + \beta_8 \text{education}_i) \\
 &+ \beta_9 d_j + \varepsilon_{ij}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $medical_{ij}$ captures access to medical care of respondent i in region j . $medbribe_i$ is a binary measure of the respondent's own experience of paying a bribe for treatment at a public clinic or hospital and $regmedbribe_j$ is the regional (sub-national survey area) incidence of medical corruption. Including both own experience and the regional incidence allows us to examine the effect of the local level of corruption, holding constant the respondent's own experience of paying a bribe (Breen and Gillanders, 2022).

$female_i$ takes a value of one if the respondent is female, age_i is the respondent's age, and $education_i$ is a categorical variable capturing the respondent's highest completed level of education. $poverty_i$ is based on the respondent's self-reported shortage of cash income. It is a binary variable that takes 1 if the respondent or anyone in their family has always gone without a cash income and 0 otherwise. $Urban_i$ is a binary variable indicating that the respondent lives in an urban primary sampling unit (PSU). $Healthinfrast_i$ is also a binary variable indicating the presence of health infrastructure in or near the PSU. We include country fixed effects (d_j) in all specifications to account for cross country differences in the level of access to medical care. We also cluster the standard errors at the regional level. ε_{ij} is the error term.

Results

To understand the relationship between medical corruption and access to medical care we start by plotting the national averages of these variables against each other in Figure 2. As shown in the figure, a lower incidence of medical corruption is correlated with a higher level of access to medical care. The visual correlation is supported by the Spearman correlation at the 1% significance level ($r= 0.614$). We can see that countries like Mauritius, CaboVerde, and Namibia which have lower rates of medical corruption tend to have better access to medical care. On the other hand, we can also see that countries like Liberia, Uganda, Sierra Leone, Guinea and Angola which have less control over medical corruption tend to have less access to medical care.

Figure 2. Control of Medical Corruption and Access to Medical Care

Note: To plot the figure, we consider having no access to be equivalent to always going without medicines or medical treatment. We create a binary variable from this information, *healthaccessdum*, that takes a value of one if the respondent answers “always” and zero otherwise. In addition, we create a dummy variable, pay a bribe for treatment at a public clinic or hospital, *medbribedum*, which takes a value of one if the respondents say that they have at least paid a bribe once and zero if they never did so. We take the inverse of these variables and their corresponding logarithm to facilitate the reading of the figure.

Table 2 presents the results from our ordered probit model. Our main finding is that the regional incidence of medical corruption is strongly associated with the respondent’s access to medical care. The estimated marginal effects are statistically significant and of an appreciable magnitude. To take the most and least desirable categories for example, a one standard deviation increase in the regional incidence of medical corruption (0.101) reduces the likelihood of the respondent reporting that they have never gone without access to medical care by 4.1% and increases the likelihood that they report always going without access by 0.8%. For comparison, the marginal effect of there being a health clinic in the PSU is a 2.4% increase in the likelihood of always having access and a 0.5% reduction in the likelihood of never having access. In terms of the other controls, urban residents are more likely to have access to healthcare services. Being poor, that is without a cash income, is

significantly and meaningfully associated with a higher likelihood of being without medical care. Older people are less likely to have access to medicine and medical treatment. Finally, women are more likely to have access to medical care. We also find that those who pay bribes are less likely to have access. Using Round 7 data as a robustness check, we find a similar result: medical corruption restricts access to medicine and medical treatment in Africa (Table A1).

Table 2. Ordered probit models: medical corruption and access to medical care (round 8)

How often gone without medical care	“Never ” (1)	“Just once or twice” (2)	“Several times” (3)	“Many times” (4)	“Always/No Access” (5)
Own experience of medical bribery	-0.073733 *** (0.00693)	-0.0054263 *** (0.00086)	0.0259498 *** (0.00214)	0.0357947 *** (0.00368)	0.0174148*** (0.00209)
Regional incidence of medical bribery	-0.4049687 *** (0.06747)	-0.0131864*** (0.00352)	0.1539621*** (0.02573)	0.1834933 *** (.03102)	0.0806996 *** (0.0137)
Health Infrastructure	0.0244469 *** (0.007)	0.0008846*** (0.00035)	-0.0092371*** (0.00266)	-0.0111473 *** (.00324)	-0.0049471 *** (0.00143)
Urban Area	0.0687089 *** (0.00753)	0.0019231*** (0.0005)	-0.0262501*** (0.00308)	-0.0308796*** (0.00326)	-0.0135024*** (0.00158)
Education	0.0225909 *** (0.00279)	0.0007356 *** (0.00019)	-0.0085887*** (0.00109)	-0.0102361*** (0.00128)	-0.0045018*** (0.0006)
Poverty	-0.1530754*** (0.00381)	-0.0049844*** (0.00111)	0.0581966*** (0.00257)	0.0693592 *** (0.00197)	0.0305039 *** (0.00126)
Female	0.0129734*** (0.00391)	0.0004223*** (0.00015)	-0.0049319*** (0.00148)	-0.0058782 *** (0.00177)	-0.0025856 *** (0.00079)
Age	-0.0010722*** (0.00018)	-0.0000349*** (0.00001)	0.0004076*** (0.00007)	0.0004858*** (0.00008)	0.0002137*** (0.00004)
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	47,074	47,074	47,074	47,074	47,074

Note: Standard errors are clustered by region and reported in parentheses. All specifications include country fixed effects. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Corruption in general has been found to weaken the quality of governance and institutional quality of a state (Downie, 2013; Sewall, 2016; Singh, 2022). It has also been shown to be detrimental to entrepreneurship (Dutta and Sobel, 2016), firm growth (Fisman and Svensson, 2007), income equality (Gupta et al., 2002), human development (Ortega et al., 2013), and economic development growth and development Mauro (1995). Through its effects on economic development, investment and regulation, corruption in general could restrict access to health services by sanding the wheels of an economy. In Table 3, we therefore include the regional incidence of bribery in other domains: namely the regional incidence of bribery in the public-school services, the issuing of identity documents, and interactions with the police. Table 3 shows that non-medical corruption only has a weak association with health access. The estimated marginal effects of non-medical corruption are a fraction of the magnitude of medical corruption and fall short of the 5% level of statistical

significance. While the inclusion of other corruption reduces the marginal effect of medical corruption somewhat, the estimated relationship between medical corruption and access to health care remains significant and of a meaningful magnitude.⁵ We conclude that in terms of facilitating access to healthcare, it is medical corruption that must be fought.

Table 3. Medical corruption and access to medical care: accounting for regional incidence of bribery in other domains (round 8)

How often gone without medical care	“Never ” (0)	“Just once or twice”(1)	“Several times”(2)	“Many times”(3)	“Always/No Access”(4)
Own experience of medical bribery	-0.0737627 *** (0.00693)	-0.0054315 *** (0.00086)	0.0259655*** (0.00213)	0.0358131 *** (0.00368)	0.0174155*** (0.0021)
Regional incidence of medical bribery	-0.3158565*** (0.08109)	-0.0102885*** (0.00348)	0.1201081 ** (0.03086)	0.1431244*** (0.037)	0.0629125*** (.01639)
Regional incidence of other briberies	-0.1055576* (0.05572)	-0.0034384* (0.00188)	0.0401395* (0.0212)	0.0478315* (0.02525)	0.021025* (0.01107)
Health Infrastructure	0.0243969*** (0.00696)	0.000883 *** (0.00034)	-0.0092203*** (0.00265)	-0.0111251 *** (0.00322)	-0.0049345*** (0.00142)
Urban Area	0.0704989*** (0.00754)	0.0019654 *** (0.00051)	-0.0269412*** (0.00309)	-0.0316789*** (0.00327)	-0.0138442*** (0.00158)
Education	0.0230377*** (0.00281)	0.0007504*** (0.00019)	-0.0087603*** (0.0011)	-0.0104391*** (0.00129)	-0.0045887*** (0.00061)
Poverty	-0.1529198*** (0.00382)	-0.0049811*** (0.0011)	0.0581495 *** (0.00258)	0.0692927 *** (0.00198)	0.0304587*** (0.00126)
Female	0.0130715*** (0.00391)	0.0004257*** (0.00015)	-0.0049702*** (0.00148)	-0.005923 *** (0.00177)	-0.002604 *** (0.00079)
Age	-0.0010684 *** (0.00018)	-0.0000348*** (0.00001)	0.0004063 *** (0.00007)	0.0004841*** (0.00008)	0.0002128 *** (0.00004)
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	47,074	47,074	47,074	47,074	47,074

Note: Standard errors are clustered by region and reported in parentheses. All specifications include country fixed effects. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

To see if our relationships of interest vary according to gender⁶, we split the sample by self-reported gender and estimated the models from Table 3 for each group. Table 4 shows that medical corruption is associated with a lack of access for both men and women. The estimated marginal effects for women are, if anything, somewhat smaller. This may be due to specific government programs for women and children in the health sector in many African countries⁷ and international programmes from NGOs and other international development actors.

⁵ Table A2 in the appendix shows that the Round 7 data yields very similar conclusions.

⁶ Unequal divisions of resources in the household is probably one reason. In addition, Sen (1998) argues that because of gender bias against women in many parts of the world, women tend to receive less attention and care than men do, particularly girls often receive very much less support than boys.

⁷ A well-known example is the implementation in Burkina Faso of free health care for women and children under five since March 2016.

Table 4. Sample splits by gender

	"Never" (0)		"Just once or twice" (1)		"Several times" (2)		"Many times" (3)		"Always/No Access" (4)	
	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
How often gone without medical care										
Own experience of medical bribery	-0.0654744 *** (0.00947)	-0.0812746*** (0.00842)	-0.0043527*** (-0.0043527)	-0.0065275 *** (0.00114)	0.0231006 *** (0.00305)	0.0286274*** (0.00264)	0.0318837 *** (0.00496)	0.0393207 *** (0.00444)	0.0148428 *** (0.00259)	0.019854*** (0.00267)
Regional incidence of medical bribery	-0.2847754 *** (0.0861)	-0.3465736*** (0.09012)	-0.0085308** (0.00339)	-0.0121742*** (0.00409)	0.1073901 *** (0.03246)	0.1331697*** (0.03475)	0.1304004*** (0.03963)	0.1553988*** (0.0408)	0.0555157 *** (0.01704)	0.0701793*** (0.01839)
Regional incidence of other briberies	-0.1326646 (0.06134)	-0.0797345 (0.05847)	0.00339 (0.00204)	-0.0028008 (0.00205)	0.0500284 (0.02319)	0.0306377 (0.02247)	0.0607479** (0.02812)	0.0357519 (0.0262)	0.0258624** (0.01192)	0.0161458 (0.01183)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	23,528	23,546	23,528	23,546	23,528	23,546	23,528	23,546	23,528	23,546

Note: Standard errors are clustered by region and reported in parentheses. All specifications include country fixed effects. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. Each specification includes the control Variables from Table 2-3.

The data also allow us to explore two additional important health sector variables: the experiences of those who were able to get access to healthcare and the attitudes of respondents to their government's performance in terms of healthcare. The Afrobarometer asks those who report having had contact with a public clinic or hospital "How easy or difficult was it to obtain the medical care you needed?" with possible answers "Very easy", "Easy", "Difficult", and "Very difficult." This question therefore probes the experience of those who at least had contact with the public health system. More than 48.52 % of respondents found it either difficult or very difficult to get the medical care they needed. The worst cases are Sudan, Gabon, Liberia, Gambia, Morocco, Senegal, Uganda, Guinea, Angola, Côte d'Ivoire, Malawi, and Sierra Leone where more than 55 % of respondents experienced difficulties in obtaining medical care. Table 5 shows that for those who have accessed the system, the incidence of medical corruption in their region predicts that they are more likely to have found it very difficult to get the care that they needed. Like Hsiao et al. (2019) we find that one's own experience of bribe paying predicts a lower quality service. We conclude that medical corruption not only impedes people from accessing medical care but undermines the quality of care for those who do get into the system, over and above any effect of their own bribe paying.

Table 5. Medical corruption and difficulty to obtain medical care in Africa (round8)

Difficulty to obtain medical treatment	Very easy (1)	Easy (2)	Difficult (3)	Very difficult (4)
Own experience of medical bribery	-0.0965329 *** (0.00432)	-0.143715 *** (0.00839)	0.057886 *** (0.00315)	0.1823619 *** (0.0105)
Regional incidence of medical bribery	-0.1020433*** (0.0389)	-0.104535*** (0.03997)	0.0768831*** (0.02915)	0.1296951*** (0.0497)
Health infrastructure	0.0076937 ** (0.00366)	0.0079632 ** (0.00387)	-0.0057864 ** (0 .0028)	-0.0098705 ** (0.00473)
Urban area	-0.0186077 *** (0.00413)	-0.0193425 *** (0.00436)	0.0139701 *** (0.00307)	0.0239801 *** (0.00541)
Education	-0.0036013** (0.00146)	-0.0036892** (0.00148)	0.0027134** (0.0011)	0.0045772** (0.00185)
Poverty	-0.0202597 *** (0.00147)	-0.0207544 *** (0.00164)	0.0152644 *** (0.00116)	0.0257497 *** (0 .00193)
Female	0.0100354 *** (0.00255)	0.0103094 *** (0.00266)	-0.0075551 *** (0.00195)	-0.0127898 *** (0.00326)
Age	0.0001397 (0.00011)	0.0001431 (0.00011)	-0.0001052 (0.00008)	-0.0001775 (0.00014)
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	28,715	28,715	28,715	28,715

Note: Standard errors are clustered by country and region and reported in parentheses. All specifications include country fixed effects. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 6. Ordered probit models: government handling improving basic health services (round 8)

How well or badly government handling improving health services	Very badly (1)	Fairly badly (2)	Fairly well (3)	Very well (4)
Own experience of medical bribery	0.063526*** (0.00861)	0.0077869*** (0.00094)	-0.0475256*** (0.00652)	-0.0237872*** (0.00273)
Regional incidence of medical bribery	0.1202913 (0.08691)	0.0217516 (0.0217516)	-0.0902846 (0.0652)	-0.0517584 (0.03725)
Health Infrastructure	-0.0047927 (0.00673)	-0.0008603 (0.00119)	0.0035973 (0.00505)	0.0020558 (0.00288)
Urban Area	0.0175504** (0.007)	0.0031354** (0.00129)	-0.0131711** (0.00527)	-0.0075146** (0.003)
Education	0.0115214*** (0.00249)	0.0020833*** (0.00047)	-0.0086473*** (0.00183)	-0.0049574*** (0.00111)
Poverty	0.0290337*** (0.00247)	0.00525*** (0.00061)	-0.0217912*** (0.00199)	-0.0124925*** (0.00107)
Female	0.0027393 (0.00298)	0.0004953 (0.00054)	-0.002056 (0.00223)	-0.0011786 (0.00128)
Age	0.000532*** (0.00014)	0.0000962*** (0.00003)	-0.0003993*** (0.00011)	-0.0002289*** (0.00006)
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	46,539	46,539	46,539	46,539

Note: Standard errors are clustered by region and reported in parentheses. All specifications include country fixed effects. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Given these findings, it is somewhat surprising that in Table 6 we do not find a statistically significant effect of the regional incidence of medical corruption on attitudes to the government's handling of improving basic health services. While someone with a recent experience of paying a bribe in the context of healthcare is 6.4% more likely to believe that the government is doing very badly in this regard, the extent to which the regional health system is corrupt is insignificant. People appreciate that corruption is a challenge in terms of healthcare reform but perhaps only if they have direct experience of corruption themselves.

Conclusions

This paper has demonstrated that there is a statistically significant and meaningful relationship between medical corruption and household access to medical care in Africa. Living in a region in which medical corruption is more common is strongly associated with reduced access to medical care. We also found that for those who do manage to access the healthcare system, medical corruption undermines the quality of the care they receive, as captured by their sense of how difficult it was to get the care they needed. Other contexts in which corruption occurs do not seem to be driving our results, leading us to conclude that to increase access to medical care in Africa, anti-corruption efforts should be targeted.

Our results add to the existing literature that has shown how corruption is a serious threat to sustainable development, thus rejecting the notion of corruption as “grease in the wheels” in favour of the “sands in the wheels” hypothesis. This cost of corruption should be taken into account in policy making. Our findings add further weight to the case for devoting substantial resources to health sector-specific anti-corruption efforts. They suggest that government and non-governmental organizations that wish to foster health capital development through access to medical care have a common cause with anti-corruption advocates and practitioners. Disincentivizing bribery by increasing salaries could be one of the most effective measures to be considered due to the low salaries of health workers in Africa (Besley and McLaren, 1993; Chang and Moene, 1999; Klitgaard, 1988; Klitgaard et al., 2000; Matsushima and Yamada, 2016; Mookherjee and Png, 1995). Supporting private health care and ensuring that there is robust and efficient oversight and regulation may also be ineffective as corruption is highly prevalent where legislative and regulative complexity are pervasive and competition low (Ades and Di Tella, 1999). Based on the economic theory of crime (Becker, 1968), increasing the expected cost of paying and accepting bribes, or increasing the gain of avoiding involvement with bribery could reduce medical corruption and foster access to medical care and the potential of African countries to make progress toward universal health coverage. Finally, setting up enforcement of anti-corruption laws and enhancing transparency by joining international initiatives in healthcare reform could also be important in this regard (Vian, 2008a).

While our work addresses a knowledge gap and uses data on medical corruption rather than aggregate measures of corruption, it is not without limitations. First, since we use secondary survey data, our definition of corruption is limited to petty corruption in the health sector, rather than large-scale medical corruption schemes. In addition, medical corruption is viewed from the customers’ perspective rather than from the perspective of other agents, for instance, healthcare personnel and government regulators. We could not differentiate between beneficiaries of corruption among healthcare personnel and reasons for paying bribes. Further work is needed to understand the behaviours and interactions of these actors. Future work could also build on our study by linking the Afrobarometer data on medical corruption to health outcomes.

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Appendices

Table A1. Ordered probit models: medical corruption and access medicine and medical treatment (round 7)

How often gone without medical care	“Never ”	“Just once or twice”	“Several times”	“Many times”	“Always/No Access”
Own experience of medical bribery	-0.0893878*** (0.00782)	0.0032162*** (0.00062)	0.0361671 *** (0.0005487)	0.035289 *** (.00336)	0.0147155 *** (0 .0017)
Regional incidence of medical bribery	-0.4102785*** (0.11973)	0.0326852*** (0.00978)	0.1745312*** (0.0513)	0.1480722*** (0.04327)	0.05499*** (0.01636)
Health Infrastructure	0.0378427*** (0.00675)	-0.0028961*** (0.00056)	-0.0160438*** (.00285)	-0.0137499*** (0.00256)	-0.0051529*** (0.00094)
Urban Area	0.0723796 *** (0.00924)	-.0060692*** (0.00094)	-0.0308608*** (.00401)	-0.0258925*** (0.00332)	-0.0095571 *** (0.00133)
Education	0.0302666*** (0.00268)	-0.0024112 *** (0.0003)	-0.0128753 *** (0.00123)	-0.0109234*** (0.00096)	-0.0040567*** (0.00041)
Poverty	-0.1658207*** (0.00456)	0.0132102*** (0.00116)	0.0705396 *** (0.0029)	0.0598458 *** (0.00212)	0.0222251*** (0.00116)
Female	0.0124062*** (0.00463)	-0.0009882*** (.00038)	-0.0052772*** (0.00198)	-0.0044776*** (0.00168)	-0.0016631*** (0.00061)
Age	-0.0012899*** (0.0002)	0.0001028*** (0.00002)	0.0005487*** (0.00009)	0.0004655*** (0 .00007)	0.0001729*** (0.00003)
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	44,457	44,457	44,457	44,457	44,457

Note: Standard errors are clustered by region and reported in parentheses. All specifications include country fixed effects. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Table A2. Medical corruption and access to health services: accounting for regional incidence of bribery in other domains (round 7)

How often gone without medical care	“Never ” (0)	“Just once or twice”(1)	“Several times”(2)	“Many times”(3)	“Always/No Access”(4)
Own experience of medical bribery	-0.0893898*** (0.00783)	0.0032211 *** (0.00062)	0.0361756*** (0.00313)	0.0352891*** (0.00336)	0.0147039*** (0.00169)
Regional incidence of medical bribery	- 0.2953031** (0.12925)	0.0235432 ** (0.01077)	0.1256428 ** (0.05514)	0.106571** (0.04642)	0.0395461 *** (0.01738)
Regional incidence of other briberies	-0.1360133 (0.09999)	0.0108437 (0.00781)	0.0578697 (0.04259)	0.0490854 (0.03623)	0.0182145 (0.01348)
Health Infrastructure	0.0385232*** (0.00672)	-0.0029483 *** (0.00055)	-0.016334*** (0.00283)	-0.0139981*** (0.00255)	- 0.0052427*** (0.00094)
Urban Area	0.0741685*** (0.00917)	-0.0062309 *** (0.00094)	-0.0316292*** (0.00398)	-0.0265256*** (0.00329)	-0.0097827*** (0.00133)
Education	0.0307096*** (0.00272)	-0.0024483*** (0.0003)	-0.013066*** (0.00124)	-0.0110827*** (0.00097)	-0.0041125*** (0.00042)
Poverty	-0.1658348 *** (0.00456)	0.0132213*** (0.00115)	0.0705578*** (0.0029)	0.0598476*** (0.00212)	0.0222081 *** (0.00116)
Female	0.012469*** (0.00463)	-0.0009939 *** (0.00078)	-0.0053049*** (0.00198)	-0.0045001*** (0.00168)	-0.0016701*** (0.00061)
Age	-0.0013017*** (0.0002)	0.0001038*** (0.00002)	0.0005538*** (0.00009)	0.0004698*** (0.00007)	0.0001743*** (0.00003)
Country Fixed Effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	44,457	44,457	44,457	44,457	44,457

Note: Standard errors are clustered by region and reported in parentheses. All specifications include country fixed effects. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.